

WEB SAHIFA YARATISH

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Internet bu yagona standart asosida faoliyat korsatuvchi jahon global computer tarmogidir .Uning nomi tarmoqlar aro degan manoni anglatadi. U mahaliy local computer tarmoq birlashtiruvchi infarmatsion tizm bolib o'zing alohida ahborot maydoniga ega bolgan virtual to'plamdan tashkil topgan.Internet unga ulngan tarmoqda kiruvchi barcha komputerlarning o'zaro malumotlar almashish imkoniyatni yaratib beradi .o'zining komputeri orqali internetning har bir mijozi boshqa shahar yoki mamlakatga ahborot uzatish mumkun Masalan vashingtondagi Kongrss kutubhonasi katolignni korib chiqishi NYU –YORKDagi METRAPOLITEN muzeyining ohirgi ko'rgazmasiga qo'yilgan suratlar bilan ishlash xalqaro anjumanlar ishtrok etish bank muamolarni amalga oshirish va hatto boshqa mamlakatlarda istiqomat qiluvchi tarmoq mijozlari bilan shahmat o'ynash ,mumkun INTERNET XX asirning eng buyuk kashfiyotlaridan biri hisoblanadi Ushbu kashfiyottufayli butun jahon boylab yoyilib ketgan yuz millionlab komputerlarni yagona infarmatsion muhitga biriktirish mumkun .Foydlanuvchi nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qiladigan bolsak internet birinchi navbatda tarmoq mijozlarga o'zaro malumotlar almashish virtual muloqat qilish imkonini yaratib beruvchi infarmatsion magistral vazifasini otaydi ikkinchidan esa unda mavjud bolgan malumotlar bazasi majmuasi dunyo bilimlari omborini tashkil etadi.bundan tashqari internet bugungi kunda dunyo bozorini o'rganishda marketing ishlARNI TASHKIL ETISHDA zamonaviy biznesning eng muhim vositalaridan biriga aylanib bormoqda Internet o'zini shakilantiruvchi va boshqaruvchi murakkab tizm bolib asosan uchta tarkib qisimdan iborat

1 TEHNIK

2PROGRAMMAVIY

3INFARMATSION

Interntning tehnik tarkibiy qismi har hil turdagi va tipdagi Komputerlar aro aloqa kanalri telefon,sputnik,shisha tolali va boshqa turdagi tarmoq knallari Hamda tarmoq tehnik vositalari majmuaiydan tashkil topgandir .INternetning ushbu tehnik vositalaring barchasi doimiy va vaqtinchalik ishdan chiqishi internet tarmog;ining umumiy faoliyating aslo tasir etmaydi

INternetning programammaviy taminoti tarkibiy qism tarmoqda ulangan hilma hil komputerlar va tarmoq vositalari yagona standart asosida yagona tilda muloqot qilish , malumotlarni ihtiyoriy aloqa kanali yordamida uzatish mumkun

INternetning infarmatsion tarkibiy qismi internet tarmogida mavjud bolgan turli electron hujjat ,grafik,audio yozuv video tasvir va hokozo korinishdag I ahborotlar majumasidan tashkil topgandir Ushbu trkibdagi ushbu tarkibiy qismlar muhim biri u butun tarmoq boylab taqsimlanishi mumkun Masalan shahsiy komputeringizda o'qiyotgan electron darsligingiz matni bir manbadan rasmlari va tovushlari ikkinchi manbadan video tasvir va izohlari esa uchunchi manbadan yigilishi mumkun.

Unda koplal yangiliklar, masalan, yadrodan doimiy POSIX ifodalarini va uzun superglobal massivlarni chiqarib tashlandi, Php.ini konfiguratsion faylidan sate_mode,php_magic_quotes va register_globals direktvalari ochirildi. Unicod ni quvvatlash vositasi qoshildi. Bu versiyani

GNU/Linux/BSD uchun dastur kodini va MS Windows uchun kompilyatsiyalangan versiyasini PHP Snapshots rasmiy saytidan topish mumkin.

PHP o'zgaruvchilarni elon qilishda tipini korsatmasdan ham ishlash imkonini beruvchi dinamik tiplashirishga ega dasturlash dasturlash tili hisoblanadi. Skalyar tiplarni almashtirish qoshimcha ishlarni amalga oshirmasdan ham bajarish mumkin boladi.

Massivlar sonli va satrli kalitlar bilan ishlay oladi. Massivlar istalgan tipdagi jumladan, boshqa massivlardan ham tashkil topishi mumkin. PHP keng miqyosda obektlar bilan ishlashga yonaltirilgan imkoniyatlarini quvvatlaydi. PHP ga sinflar class kalit sozi bilan boshlanadi. Sinfning metodlari va maydonlar umumiy foydalanish uchun (public), himoyalangan (protected) va yashirin (private) bolishi mumkin. PHP vorislikni va interfeyslarni quvvatlaydi. Yakuniy, mavhum metod va sinflarni elon qilish mumkin. Sinflarda toplan vorisligi quvvatlanmaydi, biroq sinf bir necha intefeysni hosil qilish mumkin.

Tilning oldingi versiyalarida yaratilgan kod keyinroq chiqarilgan versiyasida eski versiyadagi konstruklar, metodikalar, funksiyalar ishlatilmaydi. Natijada bir necha yil oldin yaratilgan yangi versiyada ishlamaydi. Shuning uchun unga o'zgartirish kiritiladi.

Web- server mijozlarning HTTP-sorovlarini qabul qiluvchi server. Odatda mijozlar sifatida veb-brauzerlar qollaniladi va ularga HTTP-javoblar bilan birgalikda HTML-sahifalar, tasvirlar, fayllar, media-oqimlar yoki boshqa malumotlar uzatiladi. Web- serverlar veb-saytning asosini tashkil qiladi.

Web- server deb yuqorida qayd etilgan amallarni taminlovchi dasturiy taminotni ham bu dasturiy taminot ishlayotgan kompyuter ham tushuniladi. Mijozlar Web- serverga yagona resurs korsatuvchisi-URL-adres boyicha kerakli veb-sahifaga yoki serverda joylashgan boshqa resursga kirish huquqini oladi.

Yagona resurslar korsatuvchisi (inglizcha URL-Uniform Resource locator)-bu veb-resursning yagona lokatori (joylashuvini aniqlovchisi) dir. URL 1990-yil Tim Bernesli tomonidan Svetsariyaning Jenera shahridagi yadro tadqiqotlari boyicha Evropa kengashi tashkilotida yaratilgan. URL internetda fundamental yangilik bolib qoldi. Dastlab URL internetdagi resurslar (qoshimcha fayllar) ni joylashuvini belgilash uchun moljallangan[7].

Hozir URL internetda qariyb barcha resurslarini belgilash uchun qolaniladi. URL standarti RFC 1738 hujjatida qayd etilgan. Hozir URL terminini URI terminiga joy boshatib bermogda. Semantik orgumchak torining koplav yangi texnologiyalari URI standarticha asoslanadi. Hozir URI ning taraqqiy etishida asosiy rol jahon orgimchak tori konsorsiumiga tegishli.

Internet olamida hozirgi vaqtda 390 milliondan ortiq Web- serverlar faoliyat yuritmogda. Ular ichida Apache kompaniyasining Apache http-serveri va MS ning IIS keng ommalashgan.

Apache HTTP-serverining paydo bolishi internet tarmogining taraqqiyotining stumillashtirib turishi asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. Apache Netspage Communications (hozirgi vaqtda SUN JAVA system veb server) firmasining veb serveriga muqobil bepul birinchi Web- server hisoblanadi. Dastur koplav platformalar: Unix, FreeBSD, Linux, Solaris, Novell Netware, MacOSX, MS windows va boshqalarda ishlaydi. Apache ochiq dastur kodi bilan bepul tarqatiladigan dasturiy taminot bolib, jahonning turli burchaklaridagi dastur tuzuvchilarning dasturni yaxshilash jarayonida qatnashishini va qoshimcha ustkurma ishlab chiqaruvchilar va

ular yordamida aniq bir maqsad uchun mo'ljallangan maxsus funktsiyani bajarish imkonini beradi.

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